

Polymerization of Methyl Methacrylate in Bamboo and Date Palm Leaves by Gamma Radiation

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Bamboo and date palm leaves, impregnated with methyl methacrylate (MMA) under atmospheric conditions, were irradiated with gamma radiation (2 M rods) in the presence of air. Strong wood-polymer combinations were produced. The monomer to wood ratio is 15 : 20 by weight (42.8% monomer). This amount of MMA is just in excess of that needed for complete impregnation under atmospheric pressure. Date palm stem did not give any wood-plastic combination because of the inhibiting effect of lignin present in the stem.

THE development of wood-plastic combinations by the irradiation of monomer-impregnated wood or fibrous materials has been of a particular interest, especially in the developing countries^{1,2}. The properties of cotton-wood is enhanced by irradiating samples impregnated with MMA and styrene³.

Experimental

The radiation work is done at the Institute for Nuclear Research, Tuwatha, Baghdad. The source of gamma radiation is Co-60 gamma Cell, 220 supplied by the Atomic Energy of Canada. Dose rate is 0.66 M rods/hr, and total dose used is 2.0 M rods.

Samples of date palm stem (2.4 × 4.3 × 8.3 cm) were impregnated under atmospheric conditions for 4 hr. Excess MMA was drained out, the samples were wrapped with aluminium foil and over this wrapped with electrical adhesive tape to avoid evaporation of MMA. The wrapped samples were placed in fitting steel containers and irradiated. The irradiated samples were unwrapped and brought to constant weight under vacuum at room temperature.

Bamboo and date palm leaves (shredded and whole strip) were irradiated in the same size containers as that used for the palm stem. The wood samples (20 g each) were pressed into the containers (4.4 × 8.4 cm open top) by hand with the aid of a fitting steel plate. The required amount of MMA (10, 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15 grams) were put over the wood, and finally pressed by a hydraulic press to obtain 1500 psi. The pressure on the samples was maintained by pivoting two steel nails through holes bored just above the upper compressing steel plate. The containers were covered and irradiated in air.

The physical tests on the successful wood-plastic combinations (42.8% MMA) were done as follows :

Per cent water content was done in drying the samples in an oven at 50° for 7 days to obtain a constant weight.

Per cent water absorption was done by soaking the samples in water for 7 days at 25°.

The abrasion test was determined as the per cent loss in weight after 3 hr in the abrasion machine.

Teak wood was used as a comparative blank, all sample sizes and their blanks were the same. Teak wood is used as a blank because it is widely used in Iraq.

All the physical tests were done at the Building Research Centre, Al-Washash, Baghdad.

Results and Discussion

Pieces of date palm stem were impregnated with MMA, under atmospheric conditions for 4 hr. Samples of 2.4 × 4.3 × 8.3 cm. were used. Irradiation with 2.0 M rods of gamma radiation from ⁶⁰Co did not produce any polymer inside the stem; however a thin film of polymer was formed on the outside in samples having a slight excess of MMA over that needed for the complete impregnation. Thus pointing to the inhibiting effect of lignin which is present in palm stem, this effect has been investigated recently⁴. The addition of 10% CCl₄, 10% acetone, and 10% maleic anhydride to MMA also gave negative results. The addition of 2% benzoyl peroxide gave 5% increase in weight.

MMA was polymerized in bamboo and date palm leaves (shredded and whole strip) in the presence of inhibitor and air. Twenty grams of bamboo or leaves were always used and the amount of MMA was varied until successful results were obtained. The samples were pressed 1500 psi into steel containers, of the same size as those used for the palm stem, and irradiated with 2.0 M rods. Samples containing 10, 11, 12, 13 grams of MMA for 20 g of wood did not succeed. However, using 15 g of MMA for 20 g of wood gave very good wood-plastic sheets, the 14 : 20 ratio though successful is not as good as the 15 : 20 ratio.

The negative results of the date palm stem is due to the retarding effect of lignin⁴. Another inhibiting factor may be the presence of oxygen, but the success of the accompanying blanks of MMA solutions, reduces this possibility.

Stannett has given the comparison between polymerization in liquid systems and in fibrous matrices⁵, where it is stated that the generation of radicals (which is proportional to the product of $G(R)$ and concentration) is essentially the same in fibrous matrices and in liquids. However, those negative results of the bamboo and date palm leaves has led us to consider further the comparison given by Stannett. The negative results are those involving soaking only (under atmospheric pressure) and those having 10, 11, 12, 13 g of MMA to 20 g of wood. In these samples the monomer will be present as adsorbed molecules, and may be present as separated single molecules or as separated clusters.

In such a case the monomer may be considered as if it is present as a vapour, consequently polymerization in the fibrous and the liquid systems may be different. The following factors may be considered in the comparison between the two systems.

1. The initiation step will be slower in the monomer-vapour-fibre phase than in the pure liquid phase, due to :
 - a) The concentration of monomer per unit volume is smaller in the vapour than in the liquid phase.
 - b) Effect of the type of energy transfer. In the vapour-fibre phase and excited monomer molecule will be deactivated by a fibre molecule leading to a dead end, while in pure liquids deactivation creates other excited monomer molecules leading to initiation of some radicals or other polymer-starting species.
 - c) The inhibition effect of substances as lignin, and that of oxygen will be greater in the vapour-fibre phase.
2. Consequent to the effects above, the rate of propagation will be much slower in the monomer-vapour-fibre phase than in the liquid phase.

Therefore there will be little or no polymerization occurring in woods or shreds when they are soaked only, and it is necessary to have a liquid phase of monomer present in the sample considered. Now it is possible to explain the negative results of the bamboo and date palm leaves. In such samples the lower part has some wood-polymer formation while the upper part stayed loose. This is due to the fact that the slight excess of MMA which stayed at the

bottom of the container generates a thin film of liquid MMA which is necessary for polymerization, while the upper part has monomer vapour only, that is just as impregnated fibre. The use of pressure to impregnate wood^{1,2} and to compress bamboo and leaves in this study, is to create such a thin liquid phase over the fibres of the wood, and not only to increase its impregnation. Once the liquid phase is formed over the fibre, then polymerization has a chance of starting. The effect of oxygen will be greatly reduced, because, at high dose rates the rate of initiation and propagation will be much bigger than the rate of diffusion of oxygen^{6,7}.

The physical tests made on the successful sample of 15 to 20 ratio, Table 1, indicate that the wood-plastics prepared from bamboo and palm leaves are much better than teak wood.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE 15G. MMA TO 20 G. OF WOOD

	% water content	% water absorption	% loss in weight by abration
Bamboo shreds	4.32	21.30	0.690
Bamboo strips	4.72	28.00	0.463
Palm leaf shreds	3.80	24.50	1.540
Palm leaf strips	1.36	11.70	0.464
Teak wood blank	4.40	33.40	2.710

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